

D2.1 – Evaluation methodology

WP 2, T 2.1

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Executive summary

This document is the deliverable “D2.1 – Evaluation methodology” of the eLITHE project (project reference: 101138325).

The deliverable D2.1 outlines the foundational framework for assessing the eLITHE project’s impact in advancing electrified high-temperature heating technologies for the ceramic industry. It addresses the methodologies and tools that will be utilized to evaluate the environmental, technical, economic, and social benefits of replacing traditional fossil-based heating systems with renewable electricity-powered processes.

The document begins by introducing the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology, defining its scope, stages and relevance in evaluating industrial processes. It also provides an overview of the key manufacturing processes under study, namely bricks firing, ceramic frits melting, and alumina calcination, setting the context for the subsequent analysis. Following this, an in-depth literature review examines the current state of these processes highlighting their energy consumption, emissions, and inefficiencies. This review establishes a baseline understanding of conventional industrial practices, which serves as a reference for comparison with the electrified heating solutions developed within the project.

Subsequently, the deliverable defines the evaluation framework, detailing the construction of baseline scenarios based on current operations at the three industrial partner sites. It describes the system boundaries and functional units that will guide the assessment, ensuring consistency in comparative analyses. Additionally, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are introduced as metrics to systematically measure and compare the baseline and electrified processes. The KPIs encompass aspects such as greenhouse gas emissions, energy consumption, costs, and social factors, ensuring a holistic assessment.

Finally, the document outlines how these baseline scenarios and KPIs will be applied in WP7 to quantify the benefits of electrified industrial heating. By providing a robust evaluation methodology, this deliverable establishes the foundation for the eLITHE project to demonstrate the feasibility and advantages of electrification in the ceramic industry.

The delivery of this deliverable is done in accordance with the description in the Grant Agreement Annex 1 Part A with one month deviation and no content deviation from the original planning.

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ACRONYM LIST

Table 1: Acronym List

Acronym	Definition
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
WP	Work Package
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
SETAC	Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry
VOC	Volatile Organic Compound
PM	Particulate Matter
NDZZ	Natural Draught Zigzag Kiln
FDZZ	Forced Draught Zigzag Kiln
VSBK	Vertical Shaft Brick Kiln
DDK	Down Draft Kiln
SEC	Specific Energy Consumption
CCB	Conventional Clay Brick
SB	Sludge Brick
NCPS	Nickel-Chrome Plating Sludge
FA	Fly Ash
SEC	Specific Energy Consumption
EU ETS	European Union Emissions Trading System
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
CF	Ceramic Frits
GWP	Global Warming Potential
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

MW	Microwave
CONV	Conventional
EPD	Environmental Product Declaration
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
ESP	Electrostatic Precipitators
CFB	Circulating Fluid Bed
SGA	Smelter Grade Alumina

1 Introduction

1.1 Life cycle assessment

1.1.1. Definition and scope

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a comprehensive tool used in environmental management to evaluate the potential impacts associated with a product or process throughout its entire lifecycle. The international standard ISO 14044 defines LCA as a technique for assessing environmental burdens by (i) compiling an inventory of relevant inputs and outputs of the system under study, (ii) evaluating the potential environmental impacts of those inputs and outputs, and (iii) interpreting the results of the inventory and impact assessment in line with the study's objectives [1]. This “cradle-to-grave” approach examines the entire life cycle of a product, covering stages from raw material acquisition through production, use, and final disposal [2].

Another widely recognized definition comes from the Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry (SETAC), which describes LCA as a technique for assessing the environmental impacts of a product, process, or activity by identifying and quantifying energy and material use, waste releases, and evaluating improvement opportunities [2]. Through such assessments, LCA enables the quantification, recording, and comparison of environmental impacts across different products, processes, or services. The primary environmental impact categories considered include resource use, human health, and ecological impacts [2].

Given the above definitions, the objectives of LCA are twofold: (i) to evaluate the impacts associated with energy and raw material use, including waste disposal, and (ii) to inform the development of environmentally beneficial applications and practices through a more rational use of resources [2]. Additionally, LCA aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the interactions between human activities and the environment, supporting informed decision-making for environmental improvement [3]. LCA not only supports manufacturers in enhancing product sustainability but also helps consumers make better-informed choices.

The reliability of an LCA study depends on several critical factors: (i) the modeling approach and the degree of simplification applied to the system, (ii) the set of assumptions and hypotheses formulated at each stage of analysis, and (iii) the availability of accurate and current data [2], [4]. Addressing these elements allows LCA to serve as a robust tool in both environmental and economic decision-making, potentially integrating with economic indicators to expand its scope and functionality [5].

In the context of the eLITHE project, the LCA will be performed during Task 7.1 in Months 25 to 48 of the project. Establishing the LCA methodology framework at this stage is crucial

for aligning the assessment with the project's goals and ensuring that all relevant data can be systematically collected and analyzed.

1.1.2. Methodology

LCA encompasses the entire life cycle of a product, from its creation to its final disposal. Specifically, a typical division of a full life cycle of a product, process, or activity into subsystems includes [2]:

1. **Raw Material Production:** This stage involves all activities required for extracting raw materials from the earth, such as crude oil extraction or mining for metals, and the transportation of these materials to processing sites.
2. **Manufacturing:** Divided into two sub-stages:
 - a. **Material Manufacturing:** Converting raw materials into a usable form for creating a finished product.
 - b. **Product Manufacturing:** Processing the manufactured material to create a finished product ready for packaging.
3. **Packaging:** All manufacturing processes required for packaging the final product.
4. **Transportation and Distribution:** The energy consumed and environmental waste generated from transporting the product to retail centers or directly to consumers.
5. **Use, Reuse, and Maintenance:** All activities related to the useful life of the product, including energy requirements and environmental waste associated with storage, use, and maintenance.
6. **Recycling and Waste Management:** Involves energy requirements and environmental waste related to the final disposal of the product and methods of waste management after consumer use (recycling, landfill operations, and incineration).

By dissecting the life cycle into these distinct phases (Figure 1), LCA enables a detailed and systematic examination of where the most significant environmental effects occur, providing a foundation for targeted improvements and more sustainable practices.

Figure 1: A flowchart of typical life cycle stages

Following the ISO 14040-44 standards, the methodological framework for LCA involves four main stages (Figure 2):

1. **Goal and Scope Definition:** This stage defines the purpose and objectives of the study, defining system boundaries, data requirements, assumptions, and limitations. It also establishes the functional unit, a performance metric essential for comparing products or scenarios. Ensuring study quality involves a careful evaluation of data sources and their reliability [1].
2. **Inventory Analysis:** A technical process that quantifies data on raw materials, fuel and energy requirements, along with atmospheric emissions, waterborne and solid wastes, and other releases during production and use. Key principles include: defining the system boundaries, constructing flow diagrams of the processes, collecting and correlating data based on the functional unit for consistency, reporting data to enhance quality and accuracy, and allocating impacts [1], [6], [7].
3. **Impact Assessment:** This phase involves characterizing and assessing environmental impacts through several steps:
 - a. Classification: selecting impact categories, indicators, and calculation models.
 - b. Characterization: quantifying and summing impacts within each category.
 - c. Normalization: standardizing data to highlight each category's contribution to the total environmental load.
 - d. Weighting: comparing different categories by multiplying impact indicator results with weighting factors.
4. **Interpretation:** This final stage reviews assumptions and results for completeness and robustness. It includes identifying strengths and weaknesses, verifying reliability (which may require additional data collection), conducting sensitivity analysis, and

suggesting areas for future research. This comprehensive evaluation ensures the study meets its objectives and provides valuable insights for future work [4], [6]–[8].

Figure 2: Stages of LCA methodology according to ISO 14040-14044

1.2 An overview of the processes under analysis

The Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) approach followed in this study is cradle-to-gate, meaning it considers all stages from raw material extraction to the point where the final product leaves the industrial facility. However, within these system boundaries, the focus is placed on the thermal processes undergoing electrification, as they represent the most energy-intensive and environmentally impactful steps in production. General description of brick firing process

Brick firing is a crucial step in the manufacturing process of bricks (Figure 3), where the shaped and dried clay materials are subjected to high temperatures to achieve final strength, durability, and color [9]. This process transforms soft, dried clay into a hard, durable building material and typically occurs in kilns, where temperatures can reach up to 1,000 - 1,200 degrees Celsius [10].

During firing, several physical and chemical changes occur within the clay. Initially, the remaining moisture within the clay is driven off, followed by the burning of organic materials [11]. At higher temperatures, the clay particles fuse through a process known as sintering, that enhances the brick's strength and water resistance [12].

Figure 3: Manufacturing process of bricks (firing and cooling is a combined process)

The environmental impact of the brick firing process is significant due to the high energy consumption and the emission of pollutants. Brick firing is an energy-intensive process, often requiring substantial amounts of fuel such as coal, biomass, natural gas, or heavy oil. This extensive use of various fuels leads to high emissions of greenhouse gases and other pollutants [13].

Coal is one of the most widely used fuels in brick firing, especially in developing countries, due to its availability and low cost. Biomass, which includes agricultural waste, wood, and charcoal, is also commonly used, particularly in rural areas and traditional kilns. Natural gas is increasingly preferred in modern and urban kilns because of its cleaner combustion. Compared to coal and biomass, natural gas emits lower levels of sulfur and particulate pollutants and is more energy-efficient, resulting in less CO₂ per unit of energy produced. This makes it an environmentally favorable choice, particularly in areas with stricter emissions regulations. Heavy oil, while still used in some regions, is less common due to its higher cost and substantial environmental impact [14].

The firing process emits a variety of pollutants, including sulfur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), carbon monoxide (CO), volatile organic compounds (VOCs), and particulate matter (PM). Carbon dioxide (CO₂) is also a major byproduct of fuel combustion in brick kilns. These pollutants are directly related to the type of fuel used: coal and biomass tend to release higher levels of SO₂ and PM, while natural gas combustion produces fewer particulate emissions but still contributes to CO₂ and NO_x emissions. These pollutants harm both the environment and human health; SO₂ and NO_x contribute to acid rain and respiratory issues, while PM and VOCs can worsen air quality, leading to respiratory and cardiovascular problems in exposed populations [15].

The brick firing process can also generate waste, including broken or misshapen bricks unsuitable for use. Common practices for managing this waste vary. In some cases, defective bricks are recycled within the production process, crushed, and added back to the raw clay mixture. However, in many traditional kilns or regions lacking recycling infrastructure, these materials often end up in landfills, contributing to the environmental footprint of brick production [15].

1.2.1 General description of ceramic frits melting process

The process of creating ceramic frits, which are essential for glazing ceramics, involves several detailed stages (Figure 4). First, raw materials such as silica, alumina, and calcium carbonate are carefully prepared and measured according to precise formulations. These ingredients are mixed to form a consistent batch, which is then subjected to high temperatures in a furnace, typically ranging from 1400 to 1600°C. During this melting step, the intense heat causes the various minerals and chemical compounds to fuse into a homogeneous, glassy state. The furnace environment is meticulously controlled to ensure complete melting and homogenization of the batch, as this stage is crucial for achieving the desired chemical and physical properties of the frit. Once the materials have fully melted into a molten frit, they undergo rapid cooling or quenching, usually by immersion in water. This rapid cooling solidifies the molten material into a brittle, glassy solid. If water is used in quenching, the frit is then dried [16], [17]. Frits are typically used in their resulting form after quenching as crystals or granules, where they are mixed with other raw materials to produce conventional ceramic glazes. However, for certain applications, the frits undergo an additional milling step to be ground into a fine powder.

The melting process for ceramic frits is highly energy-intensive, primarily relying on fossil fuels like natural gas and, to a lesser extent, oil. This high energy demand contributes to a substantial carbon footprint due to the emissions of greenhouse gases, including carbon dioxide (CO₂), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), and particulate matter, released during fuel combustion.

Additionally, the production of ceramic frits generates various forms of waste. Solid waste includes leftover raw materials from batch formulation, impurities removed during processing, and residue from the furnace. The process also requires significant water usage, especially during the cooling and grinding stages. If wastewater from these stages is not properly treated, it can lead to contamination of local water bodies with heavy metals and other pollutants, such as lead and cadmium, which may be present in certain frit formulations [16], [17].

Figure 4: Production process of ceramic frits (milling is necessary for specific applications only)

1.2.2 General description of alumina calcination process

The alumina calcination process is a crucial step in producing alumina (Al_2O_3) from bauxite ore using the Bayer process (Figure 5). In this process, aluminum hydroxide ($\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$) is heated to temperatures between 950°C and 1100°C , leading to thermal decomposition that removes hydroxyl groups and converts it into anhydrous alumina (Al_2O_3). Precise control of calcination conditions is essential to optimize properties of the final alumina, such as particle size and phase composition, which are critical for the quality of aluminum products. Advanced technologies and continuous monitoring are employed to ensure consistent, high-quality calcined alumina, which is vital for various industrial applications, including aluminum metal production, ceramics, and refractories [18].

Figure 5: Key steps of the Bayer process for alumina production

The digestion and calcination stages are the two most energy-intensive steps in the Bayer process. The digestion stage, which involves heating a sodium hydroxide solution to temperatures between 143°C and 270°C to dissolve bauxite and extract aluminum hydroxide, requires significant energy, primarily from steam. This is due to the large volume of solution and extended heating needed to effectively break down the bauxite ore. The calcination stage is also highly energy-demanding, as alumina hydrate is heated to around 1000°C to remove residual moisture and complete the transformation into alumina. This process, typically relying on natural gas or coal, results in substantial CO_2 emissions and other pollutants, including SO_2 , NO_x , and particulate matter. Both stages consume approximately 3 GJ per tonne of alumina produced, making substantial contributions to the overall energy demand of the process. The primary energy sources are steam generated from boilers fueled by natural gas, coal, or oil, although some refineries may utilize renewable electricity to reduce the carbon footprint [18].

Additionally, the Bayer process generates red mud, a byproduct of the clarification stage, which requires careful waste management. Red mud is an alkaline waste material consisting of undissolved bauxite residues, including iron oxides, titanium dioxide, and trace heavy metals. Produced in large quantities (often 1-2 tonnes per tonne of alumina), red mud poses environmental risks if not properly managed, as it can contaminate soil and water. Common disposal practices include storage in specially designed containment areas or tailing ponds, but long-term containment and potential leakage remain concerns. Research is ongoing to find sustainable applications for red mud, such as in cement production or soil amendment, to reduce its environmental impact [19].

Finally, though not directly related to calcination, the overall alumina production process demands substantial water and has environmental impacts from bauxite mining, including deforestation, soil erosion, and biodiversity loss.

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2 Impact assessment of eLITHE processes

2.1 Literature Review on eLITHE processes

The literature review forms a critical foundation, offering an in-depth analysis of the current state of three industrial processes: brick production (firing stage), ceramic frits production (melting stage), and alumina production (calcination stage). By examining these key stages, the review provides essential insights into current technologies, methodologies, and the most frequently used system boundaries and functional units. This information, combined with data from the demos, supports the establishment of baseline scenarios that will serve as comparison points for future electrified processes within the eLITHE project.

Additionally, the review identifies the stages and parameters with the highest impact, pinpointing areas where electrification could offer substantial improvements. It further outlines the selection of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) within the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) framework across environmental, technical, economic, and social dimensions to ensure a comprehensive evaluation of process effectiveness and sustainability. These baseline scenarios, along with the selected KPIs adapted to our project, will play a pivotal role in WP7, where both the electrified processes and the original baseline will be assessed side-by-side to quantify the project's benefits.

This chapter is structured to first present detailed findings from relevant studies on bricks, frits, and alumina in subsections 2.1.1, 2.1.2 and 2.1.3 respectively. This is followed by section 2.2, which summarizes the key takeaways from these studies for bricks, frits, and alumina in sections 2.2.1, 2.2.2 and 2.2.3 respectively.

2.1.1 Brick firing

Environmental life cycle assessment of traditional bricks in India [20]

The first study analyzed examines the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of traditional bricks in Western Maharashtra, India. This study adopts a "cradle to gate" approach, encompassing the entire process from raw material extraction to the point where bricks are ready for transport to the market. The sub-processes within the LCA boundaries include raw material acquisition, transportation, brick production, and emissions and waste management. Soil, coal, coal powder, bagasse, and foundry sand are the primary raw materials used. These materials are transported using diesel-powered vehicles.

The brick production process involves several stages: mixing, molding, drying, and firing. In the mixing process, raw materials are manually combined with water. Workers use hand molds to shape the green bricks (the term "green bricks" is used to describe the shaped bricks before drying). The green bricks are initially dried on the ground using solar energy for four days, then stacked in a staggered fashion for an additional week. For firing, the kiln is prepared with layers of burnt bricks at the base, green bricks are arranged in layers with

coal powder between them, and coal is used as the primary fuel. Gaseous emissions from coal combustion include CO₂, SO₂, NO_x, CO, and particulate matter. Ash from burnt coal is reused to fill gaps between burnt and green bricks in the kiln setup to minimize heat loss, contributing to solid waste management.

The functional unit for this LCA study is 1,000 bricks. Table 2 provides a summary of the energy and material consumption per 1,000 bricks. The primary fuel used is coal (average calorific value of 18.8 MJ/kg), with additional energy inputs from diesel for transportation. Emissions data for various pollutants are provided in Table 3 per tonne of coal and per 1,000 bricks, highlighting the significant environmental impact of traditional brick production.

Table 2: Energy and material consumption per 1,000 bricks [20]

Material	Quantity per 1,000 bricks
Soil	0.9-1 brass
Foundry Sand	0.03-0.13 brass
Bagasse	0.11-0.23 tons
Coal Powder	0.02-0.08 tons
Water	600-800 liters

Table 3: Emissions from traditional brick production [20]

Pollutant	Emissions per tonne of coal	Emissions per 1,000 bricks
CO ₂	0.55 tons	-
SO ₂	0.003 tons	0.52-5.9 kg
NO _x	0.018 tons	-
CO	-	6.35-12.3 kg
Particulate Matter (PM)	-	0.64-1.4 kg

The study considered ten impact categories, with the highest impacts observed in respirable inorganics, climate change, and acidification/eutrophication.

The economic aspect of brick production includes labor costs, production rates, and fuel costs. Labor costs are a significant portion of the production cost, with workers involved in various stages such as raw material collection, mixing, molding, drying, and firing. Production rates vary across regions, with kilns producing between 0.6 to 1.8 million bricks per year. The cost of coal, as the primary fuel, also significantly impacts the overall production cost.

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Social impacts include employment opportunities provided by traditional brick kilns, which employ a significant number of workers, including local laborers and migrant workers. Approximately 75% of the labor force at kiln sites comprises migrant workers. On average, each kiln site employs around 50 laborers per day, including molders, firemen, and casual laborers for loading and unloading. The labor-intensive nature of the brick production process highlights the social aspect of employment generation but also indicates potential areas for improvement in labor conditions and mechanization. The presence of brick kilns affects local communities in terms of employment opportunities and environmental impact, such as air quality due to emissions from kilns.

Environmental & socio-economic impact of traditional brick making in South Africa [21]

The second study investigates the traditional brick-making processes and their environmental and socio-economic impacts in the Vhembe District of South Africa. The study uses a cradle-to-gate approach, covering activities from raw material extraction to the point where bricks are ready for transport to the market. The system boundaries include excavation, preparation, molding, firing, and cooling of bricks. The functional unit for the study is 1,000 bricks.

The study provides detailed data on the emissions and energy use for traditional brick kilns in Vhembe. The emissions (Table 4) primarily result from the combustion of firewood. The specific energy consumption (SEC) for traditional brick kilns is reported to be approximately 3-4 MJ per kg of bricks produced.

Table 4: Emissions of major pollutants in kg per 1,000 bricks [21]

Pollutant	Emissions
CO ₂	500 - 600
SO ₂	0.8 - 1.0
NO _x	0.4 - 0.5
PM2.5	0.5 - 0.7

The traditional brick-making industry in Vhembe District provides essential employment opportunities, particularly for unskilled laborers, employing approximately 3,000 workers. Each kiln typically employs 20-30 workers. However, the average daily wage is low, ranging from ZAR 50 to ZAR 80 (approximately €3 to €5), and working conditions are harsh, often exceeding 10 hours per day with limited breaks. Workers are exposed to high levels of dust and pollutants, posing significant health risks such as respiratory and cardiovascular issues.

Assessment of air pollutant emissions from brick kilns [22]

The third study analyzed assesses air pollutant emissions from five different brick-making technologies in India. Measurements were taken from seventeen individual brick kilns to

evaluate emissions of particulate matter (PM), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), carbon monoxide (CO), and carbon dioxide (CO₂). The study focuses on the emissions during the kiln firing process, which is a significant source of air pollution in brick production, and compares emission factors across different technologies. It highlights the potential environmental benefits of adopting cleaner kiln technologies over traditional kilns.

The technologies evaluated include traditional kilns like the fixed chimney Bull's trench kiln (FCBTK) and down draft kiln (DDK), as well as cleaner technologies such as natural draught and forced draught Zigzag kilns, vertical shaft brick kilns (VSBK), and tunnel kilns.

Measurements were conducted following standard BIS and EPA protocols. Gaseous emissions were measured using electrochemical sensors, while particulate emissions were assessed via gravimetric analysis. Emission factors, were then calculated based on units of energy input and per brick produced (Table 5 and Table 6), providing a clear metric for evaluating the environmental impact of the brick production process.

Table 5: Emission Factors Based on Energy Input in g per MJ [22]

Technology	PM	SO ₂	CO	CO ₂
FCBTK	0.66	0.39	2.96	140
NDZZ	0.21	0.06	0.32	113
FDZZ	0.23	0.23	1.96	92
VSBK (India)	0.10	0.11	4.39	126
DDK	0.54	<0.1	5.17	181
VSBK (Vietnam)	0.22	1.78	2.93	146
Tunnel Kiln	0.21	0.49	1.56	109

Table 6: Emission Factors Based on Mass of Fired Brick in g per kg [22]

Technology	PM	SO ₂	CO	CO ₂
FCBTK	0.89	0.52	3.63	179
NDZZ	0.22	0.06	0.35	119
FDZZ	0.24	0.24	2.04	96
VSBK (India)	0.09	0.10	4.14	118
DDK	1.56	<0.01	5.01	526
VSBK (Vietnam)	0.12	0.97	1.59	79
Tunnel Kiln	0.31	0.72	2.28	149

Atmospheric emissions and energy metrics from clamp kilns [23]

The fourth study focuses on quantifying atmospheric emissions from clamp kilns in the clay brick industry. Using a model kiln that simulates the conditions of a full-scale clamp kiln, the study measures emissions of different pollutants. Emission factors were determined per brick (Table 7). The mass of each brick used in the study is approximately 3 kg.

Table 7: Atmospheric emission factors per in g per one brick [23]

Pollutant	Emission Factor [g/brick]
CO	22.5 ± 18.8
NO	0.14 ± 0.1
NO ₂	0.0
SO ₂	1.07 ± 0.7
CO ₂	378 ± 223
PM10	0.96 ± 0.5
Hydrocarbons	1.53

The brick making process consists of three main stages:

1. Preparation: Clay is crushed, screened, milled, and mixed to achieve a homogeneous mixture. Fuel is mixed into the clay as body fuel.
2. Molding: Bricks are molded and dried before firing.
3. Firing: Bricks are stacked and fired in the clamp kiln using external fuel and body fuel.

The study varies key parameters including the source of green bricks, intrinsic properties of green bricks (moisture content and clay type), processing and packing methods, fuel type and composition, and firing start-up methods (fire-box, diesel, natural gas), as well as combustion conditions.

The specific energy consumption (SEC) for clamp kilns in the South African industry is reported as 3.4 MJ/kg of fired bricks. However, the study found that optimized firing conditions could reduce the SEC significantly, with an average SEC of 2.6 MJ/kg for all batches studied. This represents a potential energy reduction of 0.8 to 0.9 MJ/kg (32-36%), leading to significant savings in energy costs and a corresponding reduction in atmospheric emissions.

Key recommendations for enhancing energy efficiency include achieving homogeneity in fuel and clay through thorough processing, monitoring kiln temperature with distributed thermocouples for consistent firing, and using low-sulfur fuels to lower emissions and boost combustion efficiency. It is suggested to optimize energy consumption to approximately 2.5 MJ/kg without compromising firing quality, and to ensure adequate sun drying of bricks before firing to reduce energy needs for water-smoking.

Life cycle assessment of brick production in Thailand [24]

The fifth study provides a comparative life cycle assessment (LCA) of brick production in Thailand, focusing on the use of different biomass fuels for firing. The study adopts a cradle-to-gate approach, including biomass production, transport of clay and biomass, mixing of raw materials, drying of raw bricks, and firing. The functional unit is defined as one square meter of produced fired bricks, which corresponds to 121 bricks.

The study compared three biomass fuels: cane leaves, rice straw, and rice husk, used during the firing stage of brick production. The LCA was conducted using both attributional and consequential modeling approaches, and data were obtained from the Ecoinvent v.3 [25] and Thai National Life Cycle Inventory (TH-LCI) databases. The environmental impacts were assessed using the Stepwise2006 method. The emissions for the three biomass scenarios are summarized in Table 8.

Table 8: Comparative LCA results in kg CO₂-eq per m² of bricks for three biomass scenarios [24]

Impact Category	Cane Leaves	Rice Straw	Rice Husk
Global Warming	2.75 - 3.44	10.28 - 11.55	12.08 - 13.38
Respiratory Inorganics	0.006 - 0.007	0.007 - 0.014	0.019 - 0.027
Respiratory Organics	0.064 - 0.078	0.064 - 0.083	0.172 - 0.193
Nature Occupation	0.032 - 0.052	0.022 - 0.042	0.322 - 0.549
Aquatic Eutrophication	0.003 - 0.005	0.003 - 0.010	0.039 - 0.041
Mineral Extraction	0.040 - 0.080	0.050 - 0.125	0.100 - 1.270

The firing process was identified as the most impactful stage for cane leaves and rice straw scenarios. For the rice husk scenario, rice cultivation, including fertilizer use, was the primary contributor to environmental impacts.

Life cycle assessment of traditional and alternative bricks [26]

The sixth study reviewed examines the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of traditional and alternative bricks, addressing the environmental impacts of brick production from raw material extraction to disposal. This review covers traditional bricks (TB), alternative bricks with organic additives (ABO), and alternative bricks with inorganic additives (ABI). Key impact categories include climate change, human toxicity, and freshwater ecotoxicity, with the drying, and burning processes identified as having the highest impacts.

Traditional bricks are made from clay and are fired at high temperatures (1000-1200°C). ABO bricks include agricultural wastes like rice husk and wheat straw, while ABI bricks use industrial wastes like fly ash and slag, often replacing the firing process with stabilization

using binders like Portland cement. The study compares energy consumption, raw material use, and water use for these brick types (Table 9).

Table 9: Energy consumption, raw materials and water use per brick for different brick types [26]

Brick Type	Energy Consumption [MJ/brick]	Raw Materials [kg/brick]	Water [liters/brick]
Traditional Bricks (TB)	2-5	– Clay: 2.5	0.5-0.8
Alternative Bricks (ABO)	1.5-3	– Clay: 2-2.5, – Organic Additives: 0.2-0.5	0.4-0.7
Alternative Bricks (ABI)	0.5-1.5	– Clay: 1.5-2, – Inorganic Additives: 0.5-1 – Binders: 0.1-0.3	0.3-0.6

Most LCA studies on traditional bricks use a cradle-to-grave approach, while studies on alternative bricks often use a cradle-to-gate approach due to the difficulty in assessing use and end-of-life stages. SimaPro software [27] and Ecoinvent database [25] are commonly used for these assessments, with ReCiPe [28] and CML 2001 [29] being the most frequently employed LCIA methods. The study also provides data on CO₂ equivalent emissions using different approaches and functional units (Table 10).

Table 10: Emissions for different brick types evaluated through different LCA frameworks [26]

Functional Unit & Approach	Brick Type	Emissions [kg CO ₂ eq]
1,000 Bricks (Cradle-to-Gate)	Traditional Bricks (TB)	200 – 600
	Alternative Bricks with Organic Additives (ABO)	150 – 400
	Alternative Bricks with Inorganic Additives (ABI)	100 – 300
1 m ² of Wall (Cradle-to-Grave)	Traditional Bricks (TB)	40 – 80
	Alternative Bricks with Inorganic Additives (ABI)	30 – 60
1 kg of Bricks (Cradle-to-Gate)	Alternative Bricks with Inorganic Additives (ABI)	0.1 – 0.3

Social impacts include significant employment generation due to the labor-intensive nature of brick production. Traditional brick-making processes often involve harsh working

conditions, including exposure to high temperatures and dust. The use of alternative materials and methods can potentially improve working conditions by reducing the need for high-temperature firing. Emissions from brick kilns contribute to air pollution, adversely affecting the health of workers and nearby communities. Cleaner technologies and alternative brick production methods can help reduce health risks by lowering emissions. Economic impacts of brick production vary by type of brick (Table 11).

Table 11: Economic KPIs measured per one brick for different brick types [26]

Economic KPIs	Traditional Bricks (TB)	Alternative Bricks with Organic Additives (ABO)	Alternative Bricks with Inorganic Additives (ABI)
Cost of Production [\$/brick]	0.10 - 0.15	0.08 - 0.12	0.07 - 0.10
Energy Consumption [MJ/brick]	2-5	Up to 50% lower	Up to 50% lower
Market Price [\$/brick]	0.15 - 0.20	Competitive, often slightly lower	Competitive, often slightly lower

The study suggests that using waste materials in brick production can significantly reduce environmental impacts. Transitioning to alternative brick production may require initial investments in new technologies and equipment, but long-term savings from reduced energy consumption and potential environmental benefits can offset these initial costs.

LCA of clay bricks incorporating sludge and fly ash [30]

The seventh study focuses on kiln-fired clay bricks incorporating nickel-chrome plating sludge (NCPS) and fly ash (FA). This study evaluates the environmental impacts of these sludge bricks (SBs) compared to conventional clay bricks (CCBs). The composition of the sludge brick is 50% clay, 12.5% sludge and 37.5% fly ash.

The LCA adopts a cradle-to-gate approach, encompassing raw material extraction, transportation, processing, and production processes. The study utilized primary experimental data, government reports, and the Ecoinvent v3.8 database [31]. The ReCiPe-2016 method [28] was applied for impact assessment using 1,000 bricks as functional unit. The emissions for each brick type production process are summarized in Table 12.

The specific energy consumption (SEC) for firing the bricks was also assessed. For SBs, the SEC was found to be significantly lower compared to CCBs: 2.6 compared to 3.4 MJ per kg of fired bricks. The firing stage was identified as the most impactful stage of the brick production process. It is responsible for the majority of emissions and energy consumption, highlighting the importance of optimizing this stage to achieve significant environmental benefits.

Table 12: Emissions [kg] from the production process of SBs and CCBs per 1,000 bricks [30]

Pollutant	SBs [kg/1,000 bricks]	CCBs [kg/1,000 bricks]
CO ₂	180-280	400-450
SO ₂	0.30-0.45	0.80-1.0
NO _x	0.15-0.25	0.35-0.50
PM10	0.20-0.30	0.40-0.60

The LCA results indicate that SBs have a significantly lower environmental impact compared to CCBs: compared to clay bricks, SBs caused 30%, 43%, and 51% lower harm to ecosystem quality, human health, and resource categories in the endpoint assessment. Kiln emissions, coal, clay, and transportation were chief contributors, but their cumulative endpoint impacts significantly reduced (38%, 52%, 55%, and 45%) on switching to the SBs.

2.1.2 Ceramic frits melting

Energy Consumption and CO₂ Emissions of the European Glass Industry [32]

This study analyzes the energy consumption and CO₂ emissions of the European glass industry, focusing on its environmental, technical, and economic aspects. It uses data from the EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS) for 2005–2007, which provides verified emissions data covering direct emissions from fuel combustion and processes, as well as indirect emissions from electricity consumption. These data serve as the foundation for calculating intensity metrics such as CO₂ emissions and energy use per tonne of product, enabling a detailed evaluation of the industry's performance across subsectors. The study also incorporates the impact of using recycled glass (cullet) in production, highlighting its role in reducing both energy consumption and emissions.

The glass industry's significant energy use and CO₂ emissions, particularly from the melting process, are emphasized. Cullet usage is shown to reduce both energy consumption and emissions. Technical performance is measured by fuel consumption, with cullet offering notable energy-saving benefits. The economic analysis highlights the industry's energy intensity and reliance on natural gas. Table 13 summarizes key performance indicators (KPIs) for environmental, technical, and economic categories.

Table 13: KPIs for environmental, technical, and economic aspects per tonne of product [32]

Category	Index	Description	Value
Environmental	Total Energy Consumption	Total final energy consumption in 2007.	343.7 PJ

	Fuel Consumption	Total fuel consumption across all subsectors in 2007.	284.4 PJ
	Electricity Consumption	Total estimated electricity consumption in 2007.	59.2 PJ
	Direct CO ₂ Emissions	Total CO ₂ emissions from fuel combustion and industrial processes in 2007.	21.2 million tonnes
	Indirect CO ₂ Emissions	CO ₂ emissions associated with electricity consumption in 2007.	5.7 million tonnes
	Total CO ₂ Emissions	Sum of direct and indirect CO ₂ emissions in 2007.	26.9 million tonnes
Technical	Fuel Intensity	Amount of fuel consumed per tonne of saleable product	7.8 GJ
	CO ₂ Emission Intensity	Direct CO ₂ emissions per tonne of saleable product	0.57 tCO ₂
	Cullet Use (Container Glass)	Percentage of recycled glass used in production	~45%
	Energy Savings from Cullet Use	Energy savings per 10% increase in cullet use	2-3% reduction in energy consumption
Economic	Economic Energy Intensity	Energy consumption per economic output.	0.46 toe/1000h
	Fuel Mix	Types of fuels used in the glass industry.	80% natural gas, 20% fuel oils

A review on life cycle assessment in the ceramic tile industry [33]

The paper discusses the environmental impact of ceramic tile production, highlighting significant factors such as high energy consumption and emissions from non-renewable sources like natural gas. The primary objective of LCA in this industry is to assess the environmental impacts and identify potential areas for improvement.

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LCA studies in the ceramic tile industry may use different system boundaries. The "cradle-to-grave" approach includes all stages from raw material extraction to final disposal, while the "cradle-to-gate" approach considers processes up to the point the product leaves the factory. Some studies target specific stages such as firing or glazing, depending on the scope of the analysis. Functional units are typically based on 1 m² of ceramic tile.

The most commonly evaluated impact categories are climate change, terrestrial acidification, and ozone depletion, with methodologies such as the Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs), Eco-Indicator, and CML being widely used.

Table 14: Environmental, technical, economic and social KPIs [33]

Category	KPI	Description
Environmental	Greenhouse Gas Emissions	The amount of CO ₂ and other GHG emitted during the production process, particularly during the sintering stage.
	Energy Consumption	The total energy used throughout the production process, including raw material extraction, manufacturing, and distribution.
	Air Pollution	Emissions of pollutants such as particulate matter, nitrogen oxides (NO _x), and sulfur oxides (SO _x) during production.
	Waste Generation	The volume of solid and liquid waste produced during the manufacturing process.
Technical	Production Efficiency	Measures the efficiency of the production process in terms of energy and material usage.
	Material Usage	The effectiveness in utilizing raw materials with minimal waste.
	Process Optimization	The extent of technological advancements and innovations implemented to improve production processes.
Economic	Cost of Production	The total cost involved in producing ceramic tiles, including raw materials, energy, labor, and overheads.
	Market Competitiveness	The ability of ceramic tile manufacturers to compete in the market, influenced by production costs, product quality, and sustainability practices.
	Innovation Investment	The level of investment in research and development (R&D) for sustainable practices and technological advancements.

Social	Worker Health and Safety	Measures taken to ensure the health and safety of workers involved in the production process.
	Community Impact	The effect of ceramic tile production on local communities, including factors such as job creation, air and water quality, and noise pollution.
	Employment	The number of jobs created by the ceramic tile industry also considering the quality of employment.

KPIs evaluation methodology enhanced with LCA for glass and ceramic frits [34]

This study aims to develop and implement a methodology using Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) enhanced by Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) to evaluate and compare conventional and innovative technologies in glass and ceramic frits production. The conventional heating method uses natural gas as the primary fuel in high-temperature furnaces, while the innovative MW heating method uses electricity generated from various sources. The MW system in this study operates at a small pilot scale, making direct comparisons with large industrial processes challenging.

LCA system boundaries include raw material extraction, transportation and production, focusing on the calcining and melting phases. The functional unit is defined as 1 tonne of final (cold) glass or ceramic frits. The melting process is identified as the most impactful stage, accounting for approximately 60% to 90% of the total environmental burden across all LCA categories. The study also demonstrates the significant energy and emission reduction potential of MW heating technology for high-temperature processes with potential energy savings of up to 50% and substantial reductions in CO₂ and NO_x emissions.

In Table 15, “CONV Small” refers to data from small-scale conventional industrial processes, typically representing facilities with a minimum pull rate, while “CONV Large” refers to data from large-scale industrial processes, reflecting standard plant capacity. The energy consumption of MW heating shifts entirely to electricity, meaning the environmental benefits depend on the electricity mix.

Table 15: KPIs calculated from experimental data and LCA for ceramic frits production [34]

Category	KPI	Description	MW Value	CONV Small	CONV Large
Environmental	Specific CO ₂ Emissions	CO ₂ emissions per tonne of product	793 kg/t	3,321 kg/t	766 kg/t
	Specific NO _x Emissions	NO _x emissions per tonne of product	6.7 kg/t	8.86 kg/t	7.93 kg/t

	Specific SO _x Emissions	SO _x emissions per tonne of product	4.7 kg/t	1.0 kg/t	0.71 kg/t
Technical	Specific Fuel Consumption	Fuel consumption per tonne of product	N/A	15,339 MJ/t	2,900 MJ/t
	Specific Electricity Consumption	Electricity consumption per tonne of product	1,223 kWh/t	170 kWh/t	114 kWh/t
	Throughput Rate	Production rate of product	0.24 t/day	0.36 t/day	22 t/day

Life Cycle Assessment of Ceramic Tiles [35]

This paper aims to conduct a comprehensive life cycle assessment (LCA) of ceramic tiles, specifically single-fired glazed stoneware. The objective is to identify the stages and processes that contribute more to the environmental impact throughout the tile's life cycle. The study focuses on seven stages of the ceramic tile life cycle: mining the clay, atomizing the clay, producing frits and glazes, manufacturing ceramic tiles, distribution, installation and usage, and end-of-life treatment. The functional unit for the assessment is defined as 1 m² of ceramic tile over a 20-year period, reflecting typical usage duration.

Data for the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) was gathered from 35 Spanish enterprises involved in various stages of the tile life cycle. This data collection involved quantifying inputs such as materials, energy, and water, as well as outputs like emissions and waste. The study utilized the SimaPro 7.3 software [36] for modeling the inventories, with the Ecoinvent database [25] serving as a reference for secondary data. Table 16 summarizes the KPIs for ceramic tile production, highlighting the potential impacts across various environmental categories.

Table 16: Environmental KPIs for the production of 1 m² of ceramic tile [35]

KPI	Description	Range	Mean
Global Warming Potential	Total GHG emissions, expressed in kg CO ₂ equivalent.	8.7 - 18	13.2
Ozone Layer Depletion Potential	The potential impact on ozone layer depletion in kg CFC-11 equivalent	9.48E-7 - 2.12E-6	1.5E-6
Acidification Potential	The emissions contributing to acid rain in kg SO ₂ equivalent.	2.85E-2 - 6.87E-2	4.38E-2

Eutrophication Potential	The potential for nutrient enrichment in water bodies in kg PO ₄ equivalent.	3.80E-3 - 9.35E-3	5.94E-3
Photochemical Oxidation Potential	The potential for smog formation in kg C ₂ H ₄ equivalent.	1.16E-3 - 3.16E-3	1.87E-3
Human Toxicity Potential	The potential impact on human health in kg 1,4-DB equivalent.	1.13 - 2.16	1.62

The study identifies the manufacturing stage of ceramic tiles as having the greatest environmental impact across all assessed categories, primarily due to the high consumption of natural gas and electricity. Natural gas, extensively used in kilns for the firing process, results in substantial CO₂ and other greenhouse gas emissions. Electricity is heavily utilized in stages such as milling, pressing, and glazing, contributing significantly to the overall environmental footprint.

Efficiency of an industrial furnace for ceramic frits production [37]

The paper examines the efficiency and environmental impact of an industrial furnace used for producing ceramic frits. The study aims to optimize furnace performance by analyzing the effects of different chimney positions on energy distribution and natural gas consumption. The key performance indicators (Table 17) in this study provide a comprehensive understanding of the furnace's environmental and technical performance.

Table 17: Technical and environmental KPIs calculated per 1 kg of ceramic frits [37]

Category	KPI	Description	Range	Mean
Environmental	CO ₂ Emissions	Total CO ₂ emissions from the combustion process in kg/h.	282.4 - 284.4	283.4
	Specific Energy Consumption (SEC)	Specific energy consumption for producing 1 kg of ceramic frits in MJ/kg	1.4 - 8	4.6
	Flue Gas Temperature	Average temperature of the flue gas at the chimney, in K.	1,509 - 1,724	1,681
Technical	Load Temperature	Average temperature of the load at the furnace outlet in K.	1,621 - 1,627	1,623
	Energy Distribution - Load	Distribution of energy usage directed towards the load in kW.	587.0 - 589.2	587.9

	Energy Distribution - Flue Gas	Distribution of energy lost through the flue gas in kW.	291.3 - 301.2	295.7
	Energy Distribution - Walls	Distribution of energy lost through the walls in kW.	50.6 - 52.7	51.4

The study emphasizes natural gas consumption as a key factor affecting both environmental impact and operational costs, with the furnace consuming approximately 100 m³/h, varying based on chimney position and operational adjustments. This substitution not only lowers fuel consumption by up to 50% but also achieves a reduction in NO_x emissions by up to 90% due to the minimized formation of thermal NO_x, as the absence of nitrogen in the oxidizer curtails high-temperature nitrogen oxidation pathways. Additionally, optimized chimney positioning and the use of pure oxygen improve overall furnace performance, offering considerable environmental and cost-saving benefits.

Evaluation of Microwave Technology for High Temperature Processes [38]

This study investigates the potential of using integrated microwave (MW) technology for high-temperature processes in the ceramic, glass, and cement industries. The primary focus is on developing and quantifying Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and conducting a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) to evaluate the environmental and technical benefits of MW heating compared to conventional (CONV) heating methods. The conventional method assessed in the study involves the use of electric furnaces.

The system boundaries include the main processes of calcining and melting for both MW and conventional methods, excluding upstream and downstream processes. The inventory analysis uses data from lab-scale experiments and secondary data from the Ecoinvent 2.2 database [39], processed through the SimaPro 7.3 LCA software [36]. The impact assessment phase utilizes the IPCC 2007 GWP 500a method to calculate the global warming potential (GWP) expressed in kgCO₂-eq per tonne of product. The functional unit for the LCA is defined as 1 tonne of product, specifically ceramic frits (CF) and metakaolin (MK).

Table 18: KPIs for environmental and technical aspects for MW and CONV scenarios [38]

Category	KPI	Description	MW Value	CONV Value
Environmental	Specific net CO ₂ emissions (CF)	CO ₂ emissions per tonne of ceramic frits	427 kg/t	869 kg/t
	Specific net CO ₂ emissions (MK)	CO ₂ emissions per tonne of metakaolin	144 kg/t	134 kg/t

	Global Warming Potential (CF)	Overall GWP for ceramic frits	50% lower	Baseline
	Global Warming Potential (MK)	Overall GWP for metakaolin	25% lower	Baseline
Technical	Specific Electricity Cost (CF)	Cost of electricity per tonne of ceramic frits	€74	€177
	Specific Electricity Cost (MK)	Cost of electricity per tonne of metakaolin	€34	€31
	Specific Electricity Consumption (CF)	Electricity consumption per tonne of ceramic frits	794 kWh/t	1900 kWh/t
	Specific Electricity Consumption (MK)	Electricity consumption per tonne of metakaolin	360 kWh/t	336 kWh/t

Reuse of Laminated Glass Waste in the Manufacture of Ceramic Frits and Glazes [40]

The study investigates the potential of using laminated glass waste as a raw material in the production of ceramic frits and glazes. The main focus is on evaluating the technical performance of glazes with recycled material to meet industry standards. Six brands of laminated glass were selected, and the glass-PVB-glass layers were separated. The prepared raw materials, including the laminated glass waste, were melted at 1500°C and quenched in water to form a glassy structure. These frits were then ground and applied as glazes on ceramic tiles.

Various tests were conducted to evaluate their technical performance. The study assesses the performance and quality of ceramic frits and glazes made with laminated glass waste using several technical KPIs (Table 19). Using laminated glass waste conserves resources by reducing the need for virgin materials, supporting a circular economy. The results demonstrate that incorporating recycled glass maintains the physical and chemical properties of the glazes, ensuring high quality and performance in the final product.

Table 19: Technical KPIs for the performance and quality assessment of ceramic frits [40]

KPI	Description	Glazes with Glass Waste	Standard Glazes
Whiteness (L*)	Degree of whiteness measured as L* value	93.0 (average)	92.6 (average)

Gloss (G)	Brightness of the glazed surface	2.7 - 91.9 (± 31.9)	70.1 (average)
Mohs Hardness	Scratch resistance measured using Mohs scale	4 - 7 (average 5)	5
Knoop Hardness (HK)	Microhardness measured using Knoop scale	54.5 - 189.3 (0.54 - 1.85 GPa)	119.8 (1.18 GPa)
Resistance to NaClO	Resistance to chemical attack by sodium hypochlorite	92.5% resistant (class GA)	100% resistant (class GA)
Resistance to HCl	Resistance to chemical attack by hydrochloric acid	84.2% moderate resistance (class GLB)	High and moderate resistance
Thermal Expansion	Thermal expansion coefficient measured in $^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$	55.6 - 82.7 $\cdot (10^{-7} \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1})$ (average 68.7)	59.6 - 75.3 $\cdot (10^{-7} \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1})$ (average 65.4)
Microstructure (SEM Analysis)	Homogeneity and pore analysis of the glaze surface	Homogeneous with few pores	Homogeneous with few pores

2.1.3 Alumina calcination

A Review on Alumina Calcination Technology [41]

The current generation of alumina calciners, notably Generation 5, incorporates advanced technological features to improve efficiency, flexibility, and sustainability, such as:

- Preheating alumina before calcination enhancing energy efficiency
- Cyclones for effective cooling
- Fluid Bed Joined Cooler which maximizes heat recovery and operational efficiency
- Advanced bypass systems improving energy management and reducing thermal stresses
- Electrostatic Precipitators (ESP) that eliminate airlift systems and enhance dust control
- Fuel flexibility enabling the use of natural gas, heavy fuel oil, and coal gas
- Vortex finder removal and extra manholes facilitating maintenance and reducing downtime

The alumina calcination process is highly energy-intensive, posing a significant sustainability challenge. Energy consumption needs to be optimized to reduce costs and environmental impact. The introduction of hydrate bypass systems and more efficient cooling stages has significantly improved energy efficiency. Advanced process control systems with automation allow for precise control over calcination parameters, further

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reducing energy wastage. For instance, these systems can adjust fuel usage and air flow in real-time to ensure optimal combustion conditions.

Emissions of dust and gases during the calcination process are major environmental concerns. The deployment of ESP dust re-slurry systems helps manage particulate emissions effectively by capturing and recycling dust particles, enhancing also the overall efficiency of the calcination process. Additionally, the flexibility to use cleaner fuels, such as natural gas, and advanced combustion technologies contribute to lower GHG and PM emissions. Quantitatively, these improvements can lead to reductions in emissions by up to 30%, as reported by recent industry assessments.

Efficient use of resources, including fuel and water, is crucial for sustainability in alumina calcination. The latest generation calciners incorporate wash water preheating systems, which allow for the recycling of water within the process, thereby reducing freshwater consumption. Steam production from waste heat is another innovation that recovers energy which can be used elsewhere in the plant, improving overall energy efficiency.

Environmental Impact of Alumina Calcination [42]

This paper examines advancements in Circulating Fluid Bed (CFB) alumina calcination technology, with a focus on innovations that reduce energy consumption, greenhouse gas emissions, and dust emissions while enhancing resource efficiency.

Significant improvements in specific energy consumption are highlighted, showcasing the evolution of calcination process. Initially, rotary kilns consumed approximately 5500 kJ/kg alumina, a figure reduced to 4200 kJ/kg with the introduction of heat recovery systems. Early CFB installations further improved efficiency, lowering energy use to about 3300 kJ/kg alumina. Modern CFB designs have achieved a consumption rate of approximately 2900 kJ/kg alumina, with potential reduction to 2600 kJ/kg through optimized process flowsheets. Key methods include the hydrate bypass, which saves around 80 kJ/kg alumina by mixing hot alumina with pre-dried hydrate, and pre-drying wet hydrate using heat recovered from the fluid bed cooler.

The paper underscores the strong link between reduced fuel consumption and lower greenhouse gas emissions, emphasizing how these technological advancements contribute to more environmentally friendly CFB calciners, addressing growing concerns over climate change. Dust emission control is another critical focus. Historical limits on dust emissions have been significantly tightened, with modern targets set below 20 mg/Nm³ (wet). To meet these standards, hybrid filters combining electrostatic precipitators (ESP) and fabric filters have been developed. This innovative approach ensures compliance even during operational fluctuations, achieving over a 50% reduction in acceptable stack dust emission levels over time.

Finally, the paper discusses improvements in material and energy efficiency within the calcination process. Enhanced fluid bed cooler designs have increased heat transfer efficiency by 50–60%, improving operational performance. Additionally, reduced material

consumption minimizes transport volumes and energy use, lowering costs and making the overall construction process more sustainable and economical.

Environmental Impacts of Alumina Production Using Life Cycle Assessment [43]

The paper examines the Bayer process for alumina production using a comprehensive Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) approach. The primary aim is to assess the environmental impacts associated with energy consumption during the Bayer process. This study employs thermodynamic simulations of the Bayer process using Aspen V11 software, validated against referenced data. The LCA implementation is done using SimaPro 9.0, applying the ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H) method to evaluate various environmental impacts, including Global Warming Potential (GWP), stratospheric ozone depletion, terrestrial acidification, and marine eutrophication.

The study investigates different scenarios to understand the environmental implications of using various energy sources and bauxite types (Table 20). The baseline scenario utilizes natural gas combustion, resulting in 988 to 1260 kg of CO₂-equivalent emissions per tonne of alumina, depending on the bauxite type used. The combustion of natural gas is identified as the primary contributor, accounting for 65% of the total greenhouse gas emissions. Alternative scenarios include the use of biogas and biodiesel, as well as electrification applications. Among these, the scenario involving 100% renewable electricity mix shows the most significant reduction in GWP, with potential savings of up to 68% in CO₂-equivalent emissions compared to the baseline scenario.

Table 20: Environmental impacts based on the energy source and type of bauxite used [43]

Scenario	CO ₂ -equivalent Emissions [kg/tonne Al ₂ O ₃]	Stratospheric Ozone Depletion [kg CFC-11 eq./tonne Al ₂ O ₃]	Terrestrial Acidification [kg SO ₂ eq./tonne Al ₂ O ₃]	Marine Eutrophication [kg N eq./tonne Al ₂ O ₃]
Baseline (Natural Gas, Gibbsite)	988	0.00038	3.4	0.0059
Baseline (Natural Gas, Boehmite-Diaspore)	1260	0.00048	4.1	0.0070
Biogas (Gibbsite)	499	0.00045	3.6	0.0065
Biogas (Boehmite-Diaspore)	630	0.00055	4.4	0.0081
EU Electricity Mix (Gibbsite)	810	0.00039	3.5	0.0057

EU Electricity Mix (Boehmite- Diaspore)	1010	0.00049	4.3	0.0069
Renewable Electricity Mix (Gibbsite)	378	0.00038	3.1	0.0055
Renewable Electricity Mix (Boehmite- Diaspore)	407	0.00047	3.5	0.0061

LCA and LCC of Bayer and Pedersen processes for alumina production [44]

The excessive production of bauxite residue, commonly known as red mud, in the Bayer process presents significant environmental challenges. The Pedersen process, an alternative to the Bayer process, combines smelting reduction and leaching treatment of bauxite, resulting in an inert bauxite residue (grey mud). This study compares the environmental and economic performance of these two processes through life cycle assessment (LCA) and life cycle costing (LCC) based on complete mass and energy balance simulations.

The study employs HSC SIM for process simulation, linking material and energy characteristics to life cycle environmental impacts. LCA software Simapro 9.3 and the Ecoinvent v3.5 database were used to compile life cycle inventories. Numerical results across environmental, technical, and economic dimensions are detailed in the tables below.

Table 21: LCA results per tonne of alumina for the Bayer and the Pedersen processes [44]

Impact Category	Bayer Process	Pedersen Process
Global Warming Potential [kg CO ₂ eq]	1648	2122
Stratospheric Ozone Depletion [kg CFC-11 eq]	0.000985	0.00107
Ionizing Radiation [kBq Co-60 eq]	626	838
Ozone Formation, Human Health [kg NO _x eq]	4.00	4.01
Fine Particulate Matter Formation [kg PM _{2.5} eq]	2.89	2.81
Ozone Formation [kg NO _x eq]	4.04	3.99
Terrestrial Acidification [kg SO ₂ eq]	7.15	8.47
Freshwater Eutrophication [kg P eq]	1.86	2.92

Marine Eutrophication [kg N eq]	0.10	0.36
Mineral Resource Scarcity [kg Cu eq]	92	57
Fossil Resource Scarcity [kg oil eq]	433	652
Water Consumption [m ³]	28	37
Global Warming Potential [kg CO ₂ eq]	1648	2122

Table 22: Technical Parameters for the Bayer and the Pedersen processes [44]

Technical Category	Technical Parameter	Bayer Process	Pedersen Process
Energy Consumption [kWh/tonne alumina]	Pressure leaching	1407.63	N/A
	Crystallization	0.59	1491.23
	Rotary kiln	312.02	314.17
	Calcination	1149.29	1149.76
	Bauxite calcination	N/A	898.62
	Smelting reduction	N/A	1281.42
	Precipitation	N/A	1490.05
Material Input [tonne/tonne alumina]	Bauxite ore	2.15	2.15
	Lime	0.11	1.23
	Sodium hydroxide	0.88	N/A
	Sodium carbonate	N/A	2.06
	CO ₂	N/A	0.76
Water Consumption [m ³ /tonne alumina]	Water	4.90	34.34
Waste to Treatment [tonne/tonne alumina]	Red mud	1.59	N/A
	Grey mud	N/A	3.91

Table 23: Cost Components for the Bayer and the Pedersen processes [44]

Cost Component	Bayer Process	Pedersen Process
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Raw materials [\$/tonne alumina]	144.68	175.49
Energy [\$/tonne alumina]	55.32	103.27
Waste treatment [\$/tonne alumina]	12.46	16.89
Total Cost [\$/tonne alumina]	212.46	295.65

Environmental Assessment of Alumina during its Life Cycle Manufacturing Chain [45]

The paper establishes a comprehensive framework for evaluating the environmental impacts associated with alumina production, using one tonne of alumina as functional unit. The model, which is based on mass and energy conservation principles, treats the manufacturing process as a series of interconnected unit processes and calculates the environmental load by summing the contributions from each unit process. Environmental load indices are used to assess resource consumption, energy use, and environmental discharges based on data from the Chinese Zhenzhou Alumina plant (Table 24).

Table 24: Environmental load indices per tonne of alumina [45]

Index	Description	Value
High-Grade Bauxite	Tons per tonne of alumina (t/t-Al ₂ O ₃)	1.9094
Limestone	Tons per tonne of alumina (t/t-Al ₂ O ₃)	0.4306
Sodium Carbonate	Kilograms per tonne of alumina (kg/t-Al ₂ O ₃)	61.24
Coke	Tons per tonne of alumina (t/t-Al ₂ O ₃)	0.0411
Steam	Tons per tonne of alumina (t/t-Al ₂ O ₃)	5.3352
Electricity	Kilowatt-hours per tonne of alumina (kWh/t-Al ₂ O ₃)	202.88
Primary Water	Tons per tonne of alumina (t/t-Al ₂ O ₃)	2.2906
Heavy Oil	Tons per tonne of alumina (t/t-Al ₂ O ₃)	0.1084
Exhaust Gas	Cubic meters per tonne of alumina (Nm ³ /t-Al ₂ O ₃)	1942.10
Dust	Grams per tonne of alumina (g/t-Al ₂ O ₃)	0.1962
CO ₂	Kilograms per tonne of alumina (kg/t-Al ₂ O ₃)	269.17
SO ₂	Kilograms per tonne of alumina (kg/t-Al ₂ O ₃)	1.00
Wastewater	Cubic meters per tonne of alumina (m ³ /t-Al ₂ O ₃)	9.07
Suspended Solids (SS)	Grams per tonne of alumina (g/t-Al ₂ O ₃)	13.47

Waste Alkali (Na ₂ O)	Kilograms per tonne of alumina (kg/t-Al ₂ O ₃)	12.19
Red Mud	Tons per tonne of alumina (t/t-Al ₂ O ₃)	0.84

Life cycle environmental and economic assessment of alumina recovery [46]

China, the world's leading aluminum producer, generates significant quantities of aluminum dross, which is often classified as hazardous waste. This study evaluates an innovative process of alumina recovery from secondary aluminum dross and compares it with the traditional Bayer process used for bauxite.

The authors employ a coupled Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) approach to analyze and compare the two processes. The LCA framework assesses the environmental impacts from a cradle-to-gate perspective, which includes all stages from raw material extraction to the production gate (Table 25). The LCC approach evaluates the economic costs associated with each stage of the processes (Table 26). The functional unit for comparison is the production of one tonne of alumina.

Table 25: LCA results per tonne of alumina for the innovative process compared to the traditional Bayer process [46]

Impact Category	Bauxite Process	Dross Process	Improvement (%)
Climate Change [kgCO ₂ eq]	1090	736	32.48%
Terrestrial Acidification [kgSO ₂ eq]	2.16	1.52	29.63%
Freshwater Eutrophication [kgP _{eq}]	0.00160	0.000286	82.13%
Ozone Depletion [kgCFC-11eq]	3.13e-10	3.09e-10	1.28%
Fossil Depletion [kg oil eq]	426	321	24.65%
Freshwater Ecotoxicity [kg _{1,4-DB} eq]	0.155	0.0487	68.58%
Human Toxicity [kg _{1,4-DB} eq]	78.6	62.9	19.97%
Marine Ecotoxicity [kg _{1,4-DB} eq]	0.0674	0.0423	37.24%
Marine Eutrophication (kgN _{eq})	0.740	0.510	31.08%
Particulate Matter Formation [kg PM ₁₀ eq]	1.53	0.590	61.44%

Table 26: LCC results per tonne of alumina for the innovative process compared to the traditional Bayer process [46]

Cost Component	Bauxite Process	Dross Process
Raw Material Cost (Bauxite)	\$131.37	\$0.00
Secondary Aluminum Dross	\$0.00	\$0.00
Lime	\$0.38	\$0.00
Sodium Hydroxide	\$12.15	\$11.26
Steam	\$69.81	\$63.49
Water	\$0.78	\$0.49
Electricity	\$25.10	\$31.79
Natural Gas	\$22.86	\$7.38
Sulfuric Acid	\$0.00	\$15.61
Total Cost per tonne of Alumina	\$262.46	\$130.01
Profit from Ammonium Sulfate By-product	\$0.00	\$22.18

The study finds that the environmental impact of the alumina recovery process is substantially lower than that of the bauxite process. Specifically, the total normalized midpoint environmental impact value for the dross process is 32% lower than that of the bauxite process primarily due to lower energy and raw material. Key contributors to environmental impacts in both processes include steam and electricity usage.

From an economic perspective, the dross process is significantly more cost-effective. Producing one tonne of alumina via the dross process costs \$130.01, which is only 49.54% of the cost of the Bayer process (\$262.46). This substantial cost reduction stems primarily from the elimination of bauxite as a raw material. Moreover, the innovative process generates ammonium sulfate as a by-product, contributing a profit of \$22.18 per tonne of alumina as an additional revenue stream. Key savings in the dross process are achieved through reduced consumption of natural gas, lime, and water. Although electricity costs are slightly higher, they are outweighed by the overall cost efficiencies.

A review on discharge reduction of green alumina production [47]

The paper critically reviews various methods for reducing process discharge and enhancing the sustainability of alumina production from gibbsitic bauxite. It also evaluates large-scale applications of red mud, a significant by-product of the alumina industry.

The Bayer process is the primary method for alumina production, involving the digestion of crushed bauxite with sodium aluminate solution at high temperatures to extract soluble aluminum species. The process operates at digestion temperatures of 104–150 °C for gibbsite, 220–240 °C for boehmite, and 250–270 °C for diasporite, with a sodium aluminate concentration of 120–140 g/L. However, this method generates approximately 200 million tons of red mud annually, leading to severe environmental hazards due to its alkalinity and the presence of heavy metals.

Acid leaching involves treating bauxite with acids (sulfuric, hydrochloric, or nitric acid) to dissolve aluminum, silicon, and iron, followed by purification and precipitation of aluminum salts. This method achieves an alumina recovery rate of over 95% with an acid concentration of 10–20%, leaching temperature of 100–110 °C, and leaching time of 120 minutes. However, acid leaching poses environmental concerns due to the corrosive nature of the acids used, leading to equipment degradation and high operational costs.

Reduction roasting reduces iron oxides in bauxite to magnetite or ferrous metal using solid or gaseous reducing agents at high temperatures, followed by magnetic separation and alumina recovery from the non-magnetic fraction. The process operates at temperatures ranging from 800–1400 °C with reduction times between 18–180 minutes. It achieves an alumina recovery rate of up to 86.09% and an iron recovery rate of up to 89.24%. However, this method is energy-intensive and results in high carbon emissions, contributing significantly to GHG emissions. Additionally, the efficiency of iron and alumina is lower compared to other methods, necessitating further process optimization.

The calcification-carbonation method transforms silicon in bauxite into hydrogarnet through calcification, followed by carbonation using CO₂ to decompose hydrogarnet into CaCO₃ and CaO·SiO₂. The remaining alumina is then leached with NaOH solution. This process, operating at a calcification temperature of 180 °C, carbonation temperature of 100 °C, CO₂ pressure of 1.2 MPa, and reaction time of 2–3 hours, achieves an alumina extraction rate of up to 81.2%. The method produces low-Na₂O content red mud (reduced to 0.57%), which can be utilized in cement production, thus reducing environmental impact. However, the process is lengthy and involves challenging solid-liquid separation, which can be a barrier to its widespread adoption.

2.2 Key extractions from the literature review

2.2.1 Summary of studies on brick firing

Different approaches for the definition of the boundaries are found in the aforementioned studies. The Cradle-to-Gate approach includes all stages from raw material extraction to the point where bricks are ready for transport, typically involving excavation, material preparation, molding, drying, firing, and cooling [20], [21], [23], [24], [26], [30]. The Cradle-to-Grave approach extends the boundary to include the entire lifecycle of the bricks, from raw material extraction through production, use, and disposal [26]. In contrast, the “Firing

Process Only” approach focuses exclusively on the emissions and impacts associated with the firing stage of brick production [22], [23]. The functional units used in the studies vary, with the majority focusing on the production of 1,000 bricks [20], [21], [26], [30]. Other studies use units such as per brick [23], 1 m² of wall [26], and 1 m² of produced fired bricks [24].

All seven studies agree that the firing stage is the most impactful stage of the brick production process. This stage involves the combustion of various fuels, resulting in significant emissions of CO₂, SO₂, NO_x, and particulate matter (PM). The energy-intensive nature of firing, combined with the type and amount of fuel used, contributes to its high environmental impact. This consensus highlights the importance of targeting the firing process for improvements in sustainability and emissions reduction.

The studies highlight significant differences in the types of fuels and materials used in brick production. Some studies focus on traditional fuels like coal, which is prevalent in several regions due to its availability and cost-effectiveness [20], [22], [30]. In contrast, other studies emphasize the use of biomass fuels such as cane leaves, rice straw, and rice husk, which are considered more sustainable alternatives and are commonly used in regions with abundant agricultural waste [21], [24], [26]. Traditional clay remains the primary material used across all studies, reflecting its widespread availability and essential role in brick-making processes [20]–[24], [26], [30]. Some studies investigate the use of additives, including agricultural waste and industrial by-products like bagasse, foundry sand, and fly ash, to enhance the sustainability of bricks [26], [30].

Table 27 summarizes the KPIs derived from the seven studies, categorized into environmental, technical, economic, and social metrics.

Table 27: KPIs for environmental, technical, economic and social impact assessment [20]–[24], [26], [30]

Category	Index	Description	Number of studies	References
<i>Environmental</i>	<i>Emission Factors</i>	<i>Amount of pollutants emitted per unit of fuel or energy consumed.</i>	5	[21]–[24], [30]
	<i>GHG Emissions</i>	<i>Total greenhouse gas emissions produced.</i>	4	[20], [21], [26], [30]
	<i>Resource Depletion</i>	<i>Consumption of natural resources.</i>	2	[26], [30]
<i>Technical</i>	<i>Specific Energy Consumption</i>	<i>Energy required to produce a unit of output.</i>	4	[20], [23], [24], [30]
	<i>Kiln Efficiency</i>	<i>Performance and energy efficiency of the kiln.</i>	3	[23], [24], [30]
<i>Economic</i>	<i>Production Costs</i>	<i>Total costs associated with the production process (labor, materials, energy).</i>	3	[21], [26], [30]
	<i>Fuel Costs</i>	<i>Costs of fuels used in the brick firing process.</i>	2	[24], [26]
<i>Social</i>	<i>Employment</i>	<i>Number of jobs provided by the brick-making industry.</i>	4	[20], [21], [26], [30]
	<i>Working Conditions</i>	<i>Quality of the work environment, including hours and hazards.</i>	3	[21], [26], [30]
	<i>Health Impacts</i>	<i>Health issues faced by workers, often due to emissions and dust.</i>	4	[20]–[22], [30]

2.2.2 Summary of studies on ceramic frits melting

The LCA frameworks across the seven studies provide a comprehensive evaluation of the environmental impacts associated with ceramic frits production. Most studies adopt a "cradle-to-gate" approach, covering stages from raw material extraction to the factory gate, excluding the use and end-of-life phases. The functional unit commonly employed is one tonne of ceramic frit, allowing for standardized comparisons of environmental impacts across different studies [32]–[35], [37], [38], [40]. Incorporating KPIs into LCA frameworks enhances sustainability assessments by integrating energy consumption, emissions, and other relevant metrics into the life cycle inventory (LCI) and life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) phases [34], [38].

System boundaries typically include several key stages: raw material extraction and transportation, grinding and preparation of raw materials, melting and quenching, and forming and cooling. The extraction phase covers material procurement and transport to the manufacturing site. Grinding and preparation involve reducing raw materials to a powdery state before melting. The core process involves melting the raw materials and quenching the molten material in water to form vitreous, insoluble ceramic frits. The final stages involve forming the frits into the desired shape and cooling them for further processing [32]–[35], [37], [38], [40]. Among these, the melting and quenching stages are identified as the most impactful in terms of energy consumption and emissions, significantly contributing to the overall environmental footprint.

Key sustainability issues include energy consumption, emissions, and resource efficiency. Traditional gas-fired furnaces have high specific fuel consumption. Studies show that microwave (MW) technology can significantly reduce energy use by shifting consumption from fossil fuels to electricity [34], [38]. However, the environmental impact of MW technology is influenced by the electricity mix of the region; regions with cleaner energy mixes will see greater benefits from MW technology. [33]–[35], [37], [38]. CO₂, NO_x, and SO_x emissions are critical concerns. MW heating has been shown to lower CO₂ and NO_x emissions considerably, although there can be an increase in SO_x emissions due to the higher sulfur content in some raw materials. Resource efficiency is also crucial for sustainability, with innovative technologies aiming to optimize process parameters and reduce waste [32]–[35], [37], [38], [40].

Table 28 summarizes the KPIs derived from the seven studies, categorized into environmental, technical, economic, and social metrics.

Table 28: KPIs for environmental, technical, economic and social impact assessment of ceramic frits production process [32]–[35], [37], [38], [40]

Category	Index	Description	Number of studies	References
<i>Environmental</i>	<i>Specific CO₂ Emissions</i>	<i>Amount of CO₂ emissions per unit of ceramic frit produced.</i>	6	[32]–[35], [38], [40]
	<i>Specific NO_x Emissions</i>	<i>Amount of NO_x emissions per unit of ceramic frit produced.</i>	5	[33]–[35], [38], [40]
	<i>Specific SO_x Emissions</i>	<i>Amount of SO_x emissions per unit of ceramic frit produced.</i>	4	[32]–[35]
<i>Technical</i>	<i>Throughput Rate</i>	<i>Production capacity in terms of ceramic frits produced per day.</i>	4	[33]–[35], [40]
	<i>Specific Fuel Consumption</i>	<i>Amount of fuel consumed per unit of ceramic frit produced.</i>	5	[32], [34], [35], [38], [40]
	<i>Specific Electricity Consumption</i>	<i>Amount of electricity consumed per unit of ceramic frit produced.</i>	4	[32]–[35]
<i>Economic</i>	<i>Production Cost</i>	<i>Cost of producing one unit of ceramic frit.</i>	3	[34], [35], [38]
<i>Social</i>	<i>Job Creation</i>	<i>Number of jobs created by the production process.</i>	2	[34], [37]
	<i>Health and Safety Incidents</i>	<i>Number of health and safety incidents in the production process.</i>	3	[34], [35], [40]

2.2.3 Summary of studies on alumina calcination

The functional unit across the studies is typically defined as the production of 1 tonne of alumina, providing a basis for comparing environmental impacts and economic costs. System boundaries are generally set from "cradle-to-gate," encompassing bauxite mining, transportation, and refining processes. For instance, one study focuses on alumina recovery from secondary aluminum dross and uses a cradle-to-gate approach that includes stages from raw material extraction to the final alumina product [46]. Another study divides the Bayer process into sub-steps to identify environmental hotspots, providing a detailed assessment of each phase [45].

The Bayer process involves digestion, precipitation, and calcination steps, each contributing to the overall environmental load through emissions and waste generation [45], [46]. Calcination is identified as the most energy-intensive stage, primarily due to the high temperatures required. Different calcination technologies (e.g., Circulating Fluidized Bed (CFB) calciners) have varying impacts on energy consumption and emissions [41], [42]. Bauxite mining and transportation also have significant impact due to energy consumption and emissions from machinery and transportation vehicles [42], [46].

Key sustainability concerns include energy consumption, GHG emissions and resource efficiency. Advancements in CFB calciner technology have reduced fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions, addressing the energy-intensive nature of calcination. Dust emissions from the calcination process and subsequent handling of alumina remain a major issue, requiring solutions like improved fluidizing systems and dust collection technologies to protect air quality [41], [43]. Efficient use of raw materials and recycling of secondary materials are critical strategies. Alumina recovery from secondary aluminum dross significantly reduces resource consumption and emissions compared to traditional bauxite refining methods [46]. Additionally, managing red mud, a by-product of the Bayer process, is an ongoing environmental challenge. Effective disposal or utilization strategies are vital to minimizing its environmental footprint [45].

Fuel types used in the calcination process vary, with natural gas being the most common, though some studies explore alternatives like coal gas and heavy fuel oil [41], [42]. Technological advancements in calcination have led to significant improvements in energy efficiency and emission reductions. The evolution from early rotary kilns to advanced CFB calciners demonstrates notable progress, with modern technologies offering substantial benefits in reducing the environmental impact of alumina production [41], [42].

Table 29 summarizes the KPIs derived from the studies, categorized into environmental, technical, economic, and social metrics.

Table 29: KPIs for environmental, technical, economic and social impact assessment of alumina production process [41]–[47]

Category	Index	Description	Number of studies	References
<i>Environmental</i>	<i>CO₂ Emissions</i>	<i>Measure of greenhouse gases emitted per tonne of alumina.</i>	5	[41]–[43], [45], [46]
	<i>Dust Emissions</i>	<i>Concentration of dust emissions from calcination.</i>	4	[41]–[43], [45]
	<i>Water Usage</i>	<i>Volume of water used in the process.</i>	3	[45]–[47]
<i>Technical</i>	<i>Energy Consumption</i>	<i>Total energy used in the production of 1 tonne of alumina.</i>	6	[41]–[46]
	<i>Process Yield</i>	<i>Efficiency of alumina recovery from raw materials.</i>	4	[41]–[43], [46]
	<i>Equipment Efficiency</i>	<i>Efficiency of equipment used in the calcination process.</i>	3	[41]–[43]
<i>Economic</i>	<i>Production Cost</i>	<i>Total cost of producing 1 tonne of alumina.</i>	4	[41], [43], [44], [46]
	<i>Capital Expenditure</i>	<i>Investment required for production infrastructure.</i>	3	[41]–[43]
<i>Social</i>	<i>Job Creation</i>	<i>Number of jobs created per tonne of alumina produced.</i>	2	[41], [46]
	<i>Community Impact</i>	<i>Qualitative assessment of the impact on local communities.</i>	2	[41], [46]

3 Definition of evaluation framework

3.1 Description of baseline scenarios

The baseline scenarios outlined in this chapter are based on the current industrial processes of the three eLITHE project partners: IZF, TORRECID, and METLEN. These "as-is" processes will be described in detail to establish a reference point for comparison with the new electrified processes that will be developed by the project.

The purpose of these baseline scenarios is to provide a comprehensive understanding of the existing technologies, operational parameters, energy consumption, and emissions associated with brick firing, ceramic frits melting, and alumina calcination. This analysis is critical as it forms the foundation for evaluating the improvements and innovations introduced by the eLITHE project.

The eLITHE project aims to revolutionize the ceramic industry by harnessing renewable electricity to power high-temperature thermal processes. By implementing innovative solutions at three demo sites, the project seeks to demonstrate the technical, environmental, and economic feasibility of replacing fossil-based with electric heating systems. Thus, the baseline scenarios will serve as a benchmark to measure the success and impact of the project's innovations.

To ensure accuracy, data collection for the baseline scenarios involved tailored questionnaires shared with the demo partners in Month 3 (Annex I). The questionnaires focused on capturing details about process flowcharts, material usage, and energy requirements. Input was gathered during Month 4, followed by data analysis and comparisons with literature from Months 5 to 8. This effort has resulted in forming a preliminary LCA inventory for modeling reference scenarios in WP7.

In addition to these baseline scenarios, the eLITHE scenarios will be developed later as part of Task 7.1, running from M25 to M48 of the project. These scenarios will incorporate data and technological advancements generated in the following work packages:

WP4 – Technology development for furnaces electrification.

WP5 – Development and demonstration of MW-based calcination of alumina.

WP6 – Development and demonstration of a hybrid heating furnace for brick firing.

The development of the eLITHE scenarios will involve close collaboration with both the demo partners and the innovative technology developers participating in the project. These scenarios will reflect the optimized electrified processes and will be compared directly to the reference baseline scenarios to quantify improvements in energy efficiency, emissions reduction, and overall sustainability.

3.1.1 Description of as-is brick production process at the industrial site

The brick firing process at the industrial site involves several stages, starting from the feeding of raw materials to the final delivery of finished bricks (Figure 6):

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1. **Feeding and Grinding:** The process begins with a feeder that loads raw materials, primarily clay, into the system. A grinding pan is used to grind the raw materials to the desired consistency.
2. **Mixing and Molding:** The ground materials are then passed through a rolling mill to ensure uniformity. The souring house further processes the mixture before it is extruded through a press and cut into appropriate sizes by the cutter.
3. **Forming:** The shaped bricks or tiles are pressed using a revolver press to achieve the final form and dimensions.
4. **Drying:** The formed bricks are dried in a drying chamber at approximately 100°C to remove moisture content.
5. **Firing:** The dried bricks are then fired in a tunnel or roller kiln at temperatures ranging from 900°C to 1200°C. Figure 7 illustrates the airflow and heat management within the kiln. Combustion air (15°C) is supplied to the burners in the firing zone of the tunnel kiln to burn natural gas. Supply air (24°C) is fed at the end of the tunnel kiln in the opposite direction to the movement of kiln car to cool the products coming from the firing zone. Flue gas exits at 147°C
6. **Quality Monitoring and Storage:** Post-firing, the bricks undergo quality monitoring to ensure they meet the required standards. The finished products are then stored and prepared for delivery.

Figure 6: Simplified scheme of the overall brick production process [Source: Bundesverband der Deutschen Ziegelindustrie e.V.]

Figure 7: Flow diagram for the as-is firing process [Source: IZF Essen e.V.]

From the above stages, the firing stage is under study in the eLITHE project. Table 30 provides key data about the firing process at the industrial site. Before the planned modification to electric heating elements, a test using natural gas will be conducted at the semi-industrial tunnel kiln at IZF premises. Data from this test are more likely to be used for the reference scenario, rather than data from the industrial site, to ensure the same scale as the electrified pilot and make the scenarios directly comparable. However, the type of data collected will remain consistent. In the pilot plant at IZF, the power of each burner is 180 kW. The modification to electric heating aims to explore the feasibility of renewable electricity in the brick firing process.

Table 30: Key process data provided by IZF for the industrial site

Data type	Input form IZF
Final product unit	Hollow brick (weight of brick: approx. 9 kg)
Material inlet flow rate	4.14 kg/s 100% Hollow Bricks
Product outlet flow rate	4.14 kg/s 100% Hollow Bricks
Waste material	6% (hollow bricks with cracks or overfiring defects)
Natural gas flow rate	0.05 kg/s
Combustion air flow rate	2.24 kg/s
Supply air flow rate	16.38 kg/s
Flue gas flow rate	4.74 kg/s
Heat requirement for firing	2365 kW x 24h x 337 days (0.57 MJ/kg of brick)
Operation	24 hours per day and 337 days per year

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3.1.2 Description of as-is frits production process on TORRECID industrial site

The ceramic frits melting process at TORRECID involves several stages, starting from the feeding of raw materials to the quenching and drying of the molten frits (Figure 8):

1. **Raw Material Feeding:** The process begins with the feeding of raw materials into the smelter. These materials are mixed in the feed hopper and sent to the frits furnace by compressed air.
2. **Smelting:** The smelter operates at temperatures ranging from 1500°C to 1580°C, depending on the raw material. The continuous process melts the material, and the molten frits exit the furnace by overflow. Depending on the process, the burner can be powered by gas-air or gas-oxygen. In the case of gas-air, the gas is preheated from 600°C to 800°C in a heat exchanger using an energy recovery system installed at the exit of the fumes before the filtering step.
3. **Thermal Recovery and Exhaust Management:** The exhaust fumes (1300°C) generated during the smelting process are managed using and heat exchangers to recover heat and reduce environmental impact. In the case of oxygen-gas smelters, no recovery solution is available due to the lower volume of fumes.
4. **Water Quenching:** The molten frits are quenched in water, which is kept below 60°C by automatically controlled recirculation. This stage helps in solidifying the frits rapidly to achieve the desired physical properties.
5. **Drying:** After quenching, the wet frits are dried using hot air to remove any remaining moisture content.

The eLITHE project plans to develop a new ceramic frit smelter based on electric heating technologies such as induction and electrode systems. This prototype will be a furnace operating up to 1550°C with a production capacity of 200 kg/h. The process will start with gas-oxygen burners to melt the materials, followed by the use of electrodes and induction systems for heating. The liquid frit will be quenched in water, similar to the conventional process.

Table 31 provides key data about the melting process at the industrial site.

Table 31: Key process data provided by TORRECID

Data type	Input form TORRECID
Final product unit	Standard ceramic frit
Materials inlet	966 kg/h 100% raw materials
Products outlet	922 kg frit/h (composition: SiO ₂ , CaO, ZnO)
Waste material	12 kg/h (1.3% of input materials)
Oxygen	332 m ³ /h
Water consumption	15 m ³ /h

Fumes 1300 °C	700 Nm ³ /h
CO ₂ emissions	230 kg/h
Electricity consumption	0,02 kWh/kg of frit (country electricity mix)
Heat requirement for melting	8.3952 MJ/kg of frit
Natural gas (main+lateral)	130 m ³ /h
Kiln capacity	30 tonnes/day
Operation	24 hours per day and 330 days per year

Figure 8: Material flow in the conventional frit furnace

3.1.3 Description of as-is alumina production process on METLEN industrial site

The alumina calcination process involves several phases as shown in Figure 9:

1. **Feeding Materials:** Gibbsite ($\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$) and Boehmite (AlOOH) are the initial materials heated during calcination.
2. **Decomposition (100–400°C):** Gibbsite decomposes into chi-alumina ($\chi\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$) and boehmite decomposes directly into gamma-alumina ($\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$).
3. **Intermediate Phases (400–1000°C):** The material transitions through several metastable phases: $\chi\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3 \rightarrow \gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3 \rightarrow \delta\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3 \rightarrow \theta\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$.

4. **Stable Phase Formation (1000–1200°C):** At high temperatures, theta-alumina ($\theta\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$) transforms into the stable alpha-alumina ($\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$) phase, which is dense and thermodynamically stable.
5. **Final Product (Above 1200°C):** Alpha-alumina ($\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$) becomes the dominant phase and is the final desired product for most high-temperature industrial applications.

Figure 9: Alumina calcination [Source: Wefers and Misa, Alcoa 1987]

The calciner used is a combination of circulating fluid-bed and gas suspension vertical calciners. The furnace operates continuously and calcines all material that is passed through it (there is no waste material). Table 32 provides key data about the as-is calcination process. The industrial process currently runs with natural gas, but the eLITHE project will explore an alternative process using a microwave furnace.

Table 32: Key process data provided by METLEN

Data type	Input form METLEN
Final product	Gamma - Alpha alumina, SGA
Materials inlet	132 t/h of trihydrate alumina (very low humidity)
Products outlet	639377 tones per year (80 t/h)
Natural gas	2.97 MJ/kg
Flue gas	39 m ³ /s

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Electricity consumption	0.101 MJ/kg (for mechanical parts, feeders, pressurized air)
Heat requirement for melting	2.97 MJ/kg (including preheating of raw material is done with residual process heat)
Operation	Continuous operation 8000 h/y

3.2 Process boundaries and functional unit of baseline scenarios

3.2.1 Bricks: the firing process

Figure 10 illustrates the material and energy inputs, the product and waste outputs, and the system boundaries of the baseline scenario for the brick firing process. The functional unit to be used to compare the conventional and electrified processes will be a **mass unit** of bricks (kg of fired bricks).

Figure 10: LCA system boundaries for the firing process of bricks

3.2.2 Ceramic frits: the melting process

Figure 11 illustrates the material and energy inputs, the product and waste outputs, and the system boundaries of the baseline scenario for the frits melting process. The functional unit to be used to compare the conventional and electrified processes will be a **mass unit** of ceramic frits (kg of molten frits).

Figure 11: LCA system boundaries for the melting process of ceramic frits

3.2.3 Alumina: the calcination process

Figure 12 illustrates the material and energy inputs, the product and flue gas outputs, and the system boundaries of the baseline scenario for the alumina calcination process. The functional unit to be used to compare the conventional and electrified processes will be a **mass unit** of alumina (kg of gamma-alpha alumina).

Figure 12: LCA system boundaries for the calcination process of alumina

3.3 Selection of KPIs

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are essential metrics for systematically evaluating the eLITHE technologies. Integrated into the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) framework, KPIs

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offer a clear and comprehensive method for assessing the project's impact across multiple dimensions. To ensure a well-rounded evaluation, the KPIs selected for this project encompass four key aspects: environmental, technical, economic, and social.

The process of defining the most suitable KPIs began with an extensive literature review of relevant studies (see Chapter 2). Drawing from this review and CERTH's prior experience with LCA and LCC-focused projects, an initial list of proposed KPIs was compiled (see Annex II). This list was shared with WP2 and demo partners, whose valuable feedback was used to refine and narrow the selection to those KPIs most representative and applicable to the project's goals ensuring that each KPI adds unique value and focuses on distinct aspects of the assessment, in order to make the evaluation process more efficient and consistent across all demos.

Finally, the KPIs were selected based on the following criteria:

- Easily calculated from demo partner data, on-site measurements, or LCA model outputs.
- Understandable by both technical experts and the general public, aiding in the dissemination of project results.
- Applicable to both conventional and electrified processes, allowing for direct comparisons or highlighting improvements.
- Usable across all demos or at least two out of three.
- Expressed in standardized, process-relevant units (e.g., kg, tonnes, m³, MJ, kWh).
- Capable of showcasing the project's overall impact.
- Free of confidential information, ensuring transparency.

Although these KPIs have been pre-selected during the activities of Task 2.1, they will be re-examined under Task 7.1 once the new electrified processes are fully designed. Adjustments may be necessary if certain KPIs prove to be irrelevant for some pilots or if sufficient data cannot be collected for their calculation. This iterative approach ensures that the final KPIs remain robust, relevant, and fully aligned with the project's goals.

3.3.1 Environmental aspect

Three KPIs were selected to capture the environmental impact of the eLITHE project (Table 33). **KPI #1**, which measures total greenhouse gas emissions (CO₂ equivalent), will be calculated during the LCA modeling for both the baseline scenarios and the new electrified processes, allowing for direct comparison. **KPI #2**, focusing on other emissions/pollutant concentrations (e.g., NO_x, SO_x, PM), will be derived from on-site measurements provided by the industrial partners. Lastly, **KPI #3**, representing the energy source mix, will be expressed as two percentages indicating the proportion of fossil and renewable energy sources used in the thermal processes.

Table 33: Selected KPIs for the environmental aspect of the eLITHE project

KPI #	Index	Description	Indicative Unit(s)
KPI #1	GHG Emissions	Total greenhouse gas emissions (CO ₂ equivalent) from the production process.	kg CO ₂ -equivalent per kg of product
KPI #2	Concentration of other emissions/Pollutants	Emission levels (eg NO _x , SO _x , PM or other pollutants) during the thermal process.	µg/m ³
KPI #3	Energy Source Mix	The proportion of energy sources used in the thermal process (fossil fuels, renewable energy).	%

3.3.2 Technical aspect

Three KPIs were selected to reflect the technical impact of the eLITHE project (Table 34). **KPI #4**, which measures specific fuel consumption, will be calculated only for the baseline scenarios, as the new electrified processes will not utilize fuel. This KPI will be expressed in MJ or MWh_{th} per product unit to ensure independence from the type of fuel used (e.g., natural gas). **KPI #5**, specific electricity consumption, will primarily be calculated for the electrified processes, though it may also be evaluated for the baseline scenarios to account for electricity used in auxiliary equipment. Finally, **KPI #6**, process yield, is critical for assessing the efficiency of the electrified processes in transforming raw materials, providing a direct comparison with conventional methods.

Table 34: Selected KPIs for the technical aspect of the eLITHE project

KPI #	Index	Description	Indicative Unit(s)
KPI #4	Specific Fuel Consumption	Amount of fuel consumed (e.g., natural gas) per tonne of product produced.	MJ or MWh _{th} per kg of product
KPI #5	Specific Electricity Consumption	Amount of electricity consumed per tonne of product produced	MWh _{el} per kg of product
KPI #6	Process Yield	Efficiency of converting raw materials into brick/frit/alumina during thermal process	%

3.3.3 Economic aspect

Two KPIs were selected to assess the economic impact of the eLITHE project (Table 35). **KPI #7**, energy costs, will be calculated based on fuel consumption for the conventional process and electricity consumption for the electrified process. This KPI captures the shift in energy expenditure when transitioning to electrified processes, accounting for potential cost differences between conventional fuels (e.g., natural gas) and renewable electricity. **KPI #8**, payback time, provides a measure of the economic feasibility of the project by

demonstrating how quickly the investment in electrification can be recovered. The savings contributing to the payback calculation include reduced energy costs, improved energy efficiency, and lower operating expenses, such as decreased maintenance or emission-related costs. However, since the capital costs of small prototypes are not directly comparable to those of industrial-scale equipment, this KPI will more likely rely on data from hypothetical future upscale scenarios rather than the pilot cases.

Table 35: Selected KPIs for the economic aspect of the eLITHE project

KPI #	Index	Description	Indicative Unit(s)
KPI #7	Energy Costs	Costs of fuel or electricity used in the thermal process.	€/kg of product
KPI #8	Payback Time	The time required to recover the investment made in electrification through savings achieved.	Years

3.3.4 Social aspect

Two KPIs were selected to evaluate the social impact of the eLITHE project (Table 36). **KPI #9** will track satisfaction of the industrial stakeholders by using electrification technologies.

Table 36: Selected KPIs for the social aspect of the eLITHE project

KPI #	Index	Description	Indicative Unit(s)
KPI #9	Satisfaction by industrial stakeholders for the application of electrification technology	Satisfaction of the stakeholders in accordance with the operational yields achieved and safety issues during the operation of the production units using electrification technologies	Satisfaction rate (Rating from 1-10 scale)

4 Conclusions

This deliverable has laid the groundwork for evaluating the potential of the eLITHE project by establishing baseline scenarios and identifying Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to systematically measure the environmental, technical, economic, and social impacts of the project's innovations.

The literature review conducted in this deliverable provided essential insights into existing technologies, system boundaries, and functional units. While it served as a basis for the development of baseline scenarios, its primary value lies in identifying the most impactful stages and parameters in the current processes. This information ensures that the project focuses its efforts on areas with the greatest potential for improvement.

The baseline scenarios, developed in collaboration with the three industrial partners (IZF, TORRECID, and METLEN) serve as critical reference points. These scenarios detail the current "as-is" operations of brick firing, ceramic frits melting, and alumina calcination processes. By analyzing the energy consumption, emissions, and operational parameters of these conventional processes, the baselines provide a starting point for assessing the improvements offered by electrified alternatives. The collected data form the preliminary Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) inventory for subsequent modeling in WP7.

A robust set of KPIs has been selected to capture the key dimensions of project impact. These include metrics such as greenhouse gas emissions, energy costs, specific energy consumption, and process yield, among others. The KPIs have been carefully chosen based on their relevance, measurability, and applicability across all three industrial demos. Their alignment with the LCA and LCC methodologies ensures a holistic evaluation of the project's environmental, economic, and operational performance. Furthermore, KPIs such as payback time and social metrics like satisfaction of the stakeholders by applying the electrification technologies.

In conclusion, the baseline scenarios and KPIs established in this deliverable form the cornerstone of the eLITHE project's evaluation framework. These elements will enable a direct and systematic comparison between conventional and electrified processes, allowing the project to demonstrate its technical, environmental, and economic benefits.

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Annex I

Task 2.1 - KPIs and LCA framework definition

The objective of this questionnaire is to become familiar with the **as-is process flowchart, materials and energy requirements**.

#	General description	Detailed description	Indicative units	Input (please fill in this table or provide external files if needed)
1	Final product	Definition of the reference product under study	Product unit	
2	Block Flow Diagram	Simplified scheme of the overall industrial process to the final product under study	-	
3	Process(es) flowchart	More detailed flow diagram(s) for the as-is subprocess(es) in the eLITHE project boundaries	-	
4	Equipment components	Basic and auxiliary equipment components used in #3, their capacity, their power	Pieces of equipment, capacity in mass or volume units, power in kW	
5	Materials inlet	Materials used as an input in production processes	Mass or volume per product unit/ per hour/ per year	
6	Materials inlet composition	Composition of inlet streams	% per mass or volume unit	
7	Products outlet	Materials produced	Production in mass or volume units per hour/ day/ year	
8	Products outlet composition	Composition of outlet streams	% per mass or volume unit	
9	Waste material	Waste material produced in #3	Mass or volume per product unit/ per hour/ per year	
10	Waste material composition	Composition of waste material produced	% per mass or volume unit	
11	Electricity consumption	Consumption or electricity in processes #3 and generation sources (e.g. country electricity mix / renewable only)	kWh per product unit or per hour/ day/ year	
12	Heat requirement	Heat requirement for processes #3 and source(s) of thermal energy (e.g. natural gas)	MJ per product unit or per hour/ day/ year	
13	Operation	Operating hours	Hours/day and days/year	
14	Parameters under modification	Main parameters in processes #3 that are planned to be modified under eLITHE project	No need to describe the final (to be) state, just what parameters are under change	

Annex II

Environmental aspect

Index	Description	Indicative Unit(s)
GHG Emissions	Total greenhouse gas emissions (CO ₂ equivalent) from the production process.	kg CO ₂ equivalent per tonne of product
Concentration of other emissions/ Pollutants	Emission levels of other pollutants (eg NO _x , SO _x , PM) during the thermal process.	µg/m ³ or kg per tonne of product
Resource Depletion	Consumption of raw materials (e.g., bauxite ore) for brick/frit/alumina production.	tonne of materials per tonne of product
Water Usage	Amount of water consumed during the production process.	liters or m ³ of water per tonne of product
Energy Source Mix	The proportion of energy sources used in the thermal process (fossil fuels, renewable energy).	%
Waste Generation	Amount of waste produced during the production process.	kg of waste per tonne of product

Technical aspect

Index	Description	Indicative Unit(s)
Specific Fuel Consumption	Amount of fuel consumed (e.g., natural gas) per tonne of product produced.	MJ or tonne of fuel per tonne of product
Specific Electricity Consumption	Amount of electricity consumed per tonne of product produced	kWh or MWh per tonne of product
Throughput Rate	Total production capacity, i.e., the amount of product produced per day or year	Tons of product per day or per year
Process Yield	Efficiency of converting raw materials into brick/frit/alumina during thermal process	%
Equipment Efficiency	The ratio of the useful heat used for the thermal process to the total energy input to the kiln/furnace/calcliner.	%
Process Downtime	Duration of non-productive time due to maintenance or operational issues.	Hours/year
Heat Recovery Efficiency	Efficiency of recovering heat from the kiln/furnace/calcliner in other stages of production or energy systems.	% of heat recovered

Economic aspect

Index	Description	Indicative Unit(s)
Production Costs	Total costs related to the final product production process, including labor, raw materials, equipment and energy.	€/tonne of product or €/year
Energy Costs	Costs of fuel or electricity used in the thermal process.	€/tonne of product or €/year
Maintenance Costs	Costs related to maintenance of the kiln/furnace/calcliner and auxiliary equipment.	€/tonne of product or €/year
Capital Expenditure	Total investment required for the installation or upgrade of production infrastructure for the thermal process	Total €
Return on Investment (ROI)	Comparison of investment costs with the savings from improved efficiency or electrification.	%

Social aspect

Index	Description	Indicative Unit(s)
Employment	Number of jobs provided by the industry, considering direct employment in the thermal process.	# of employees
Satisfaction by industrial stakeholders for the application of electrification technology	Satisfaction of the stakeholders in accordance with the operational yields achieved and safety issues during the operation of the production units using electrification technologies	Satisfaction score (Rating from 1-10 scale)
Health and Safety Incidents	Number of health and safety incidents, including accidents and injuries, occurring during the production process.	# of incidents per year
Working Conditions	Assessment of the work environment in terms of safety, ergonomics and working hours.	Satisfaction score from worker satisfaction survey
Training and Skills Development	Opportunities provided for worker training, particularly related to new technologies (e.g., electrification).	# of training hours per employee or % of workforce trained

